

Studies in Heavy Metal Soaps. Synthesis of Chloride Soaps of Aluminium

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Mono- and dichloride soaps and tri-soaps of aluminium have been synthesised by the interaction of anhydrous aluminium chloride and fatty acids in different stoichiometric ratios in different organic solvents. All chloride soaps and tri-soaps give mobile solutions of low viscosity in organic solvents.

After several reported failures¹⁻⁵ the first successful synthesis of aluminium tri-soaps was described by Mehrotra⁶⁻⁷, employing the reaction between aluminium isopropoxide and fatty acids in benzene and removing the isopropyl alcohol produced azeotropically. Gilmour *et al.*⁸ repeated the process and compared the tri-soap produced with that obtained by their method and confirmed the above results.

In view of the academic interest aroused in these products and their commercial importance, it was considered worthwhile to reinvestigate the preparation of these compounds, employing anhydrous aluminium chloride as the starting material. Mysels and Chin⁹ in a preliminary study attempted the reaction between aluminium chloride and lauric acid in cyclohexane at room temperature. They estimated the progress of the reaction by titrating the amount of hydrogen chloride evolved. The analysis of the product indicated the formation of a mixture of slightly hydrolysed mono- and dichloride soaps, but they could not separate the components "due to the large solubility of reagents and products in hydrocarbons and their reactivity with polar solvents and traces of moisture".

In this communication the preparation and properties of the monochloride di-soaps and dichloride mono-soaps of aluminium have been described by the reaction of anhydrous

1. Markowicz, *Farben Ztg.*, 1926, **34**, 326, 414, 503.
2. McBain and McLatchie, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 3266.
3. Ostwald and Riedel, *Kolloid Z.*, 1934, **69**, 185.
4. McRoberts and Schulman, *Nature*, 1948, **161**, 101.
5. Smith *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1053.
6. Mehrotra, *Nature*, 1953, **172**, 74.
7. Mehrotra and Pande, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1956, **2**, 60.
8. Gilmour *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1972.
9. Mysels and Chin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1750.

aluminium chloride and different fatty acids in the desired stoichiometric ratios in different solvents (benzene, hexane, xylene^a, etc.):

The reaction mixtures were refluxed till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had stopped. In view of their extreme susceptibility to moisture in the reagents themselves or from the atmosphere, rigorous and exacting precautions are essential to keep the system free of moisture. The chloride soaps are isolated by distilling the excess solvents and removing the last traces of the solvent under reduced pressure. The products are highly soluble in organic solvents and form mobile solutions. Their melting points increase with decrease in the chlorine content and increase with the length of fatty acid chain. Other properties, such as dipole moments and molecular weights, are being investigated.

Further, the preparation of tri-soaps was also attempted by the following reaction:

It was found that when the molar ratio was 1:3, the reaction was not fully completed even after forty hours of refluxing. The reaction mixture after removal of the solvent afforded only a small yield of the tri-soaps on crystallisation with dioxan. When the fatty acid: aluminium ratio was increased to four, the reaction, however, could be completed within twenty hours of refluxing. It has also been noticed, similar to the observation of Grey and Alexander¹⁰ and Mehrotra and Pande⁷, that two of the chloride atoms per atom of aluminium are replaced with much greater facility, whereas the third is rather resistant to such replacement, indicating the effect of bridge structure of the type:

in which the third chlorine atom is held co-ordinatively between two aluminium atoms.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatuses with standard interchangeable joints were used and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Anhydrous aluminium chloride (Judex), lauric acid (B.D.H.), redistilled at $140^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ/0.2$ mm, palmitic acid (B. D. H.), redistilled at $182^\circ \pm 1^\circ/3$ mm, and behenic acid (L. Light & Co. Ltd), dried at $80^\circ/0.2$ mm, were used. Benzene (B. D. H.), dioxan (B. D. H.), and hexane^a (Judex) were stored over sodium wire and finally distilled over sodium metal.

Aluminium was determined gravimetrically as oxide by direct ignition of soaps. The estimation of chlorine in these compounds is rather difficult. After repeated attempts the following procedure was found fairly satisfactory. The chloride soap was very gradually heated with nitric acid (1:2) when the fatty acid floated on the surface of the solution in a molten condition; the solution was cooled and the solidified fatty acid was removed by filtration and washing. Chlorine content of the filtrate was then determined in

10. Grey and Alexander, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1949, 53, 23.

the usual manner as silver chloride. A little loss of chlorine must be occurring in the initial treatment of the compound with nitric acid, but keeping in view this source of error and also extremely difficult nature of the compounds, the results of chlorine content, although slightly low, are not unsatisfactory.

Aluminium Dichloride Monolaurate.—Aluminium chloride (3.59 g., 1M) was refluxed with lauric acid (5.35 g., 1M) in hexane^a (70 ml) in a bath at $100^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$ for 17 hours. The volatile fraction was distilled at ordinary pressure. The product was finally dried at $45^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}/1.0$ mm for 5 hours. A highly viscous light yellow compound was obtained. [Found: Al, 8.95; Cl, 21.88. $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}\text{COO})$ requires Al, 9.09; Cl, 23.90%].

Aluminium Monochloride Dilaurate.—Aluminium chloride (4.11 g., 1M) was refluxed with lauric acid (12.33 g., 2M) in hexane^a (60 ml) at the bath temperature of $100^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$ for nearly 15 hours. The volatile fractions were distilled. The product was dried at $40^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}/0.2$ mm for 5 hours. A highly soluble, slightly coloured compound (m.p. $32^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$) was obtained. [Found: Al, 5.79; Cl, 6.96. $\text{AlCl}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}\text{COO})_2$ requires Al, 5.86; Cl, 7.71%].

Aluminium Dichloride Monopalmitate.—A mixture of aluminium chloride (1.056 g., 1M) and palmitic acid (2.043 g., 2M) in benzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 17 hours at the bath temperature of $105^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$. The solvent was distilled under reduced pressure and the product was dried at 25 (0.2 mm) for 3 hours. A yellow, waxy solid (m.p. $41^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$) was obtained. [Found: Al, 7.70; Cl, 18.44. $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}\text{COO})$ requires Al, 7.65; Cl, 20.10%].

Aluminium Monochloride Dipalmitate.—Aluminium chloride (2.12 g., 1M) was added to palmitic acid (8.13 g., 2M) in benzene (40 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for nearly 15 hours at $115^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$. The solvent was distilled and the product was dried under reduced pressure (0.2 mm) at 25° for 3 hours. A solid compound was obtained. [Found: Al, 4.67; Cl, 5.46. $\text{AlCl}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}\text{COO})_2$ requires Al, 4.71; Cl, 6.26%].

Aluminium Dichloride Monobehenate.—A mixture of aluminium chloride (4.43 g.) and behenic acid (8.74 g.) in molar ratio of 1:1 in hexane^a (60 ml) was refluxed at $100^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$ for 20 hours. The volatile fractions were distilled at ordinary pressure and the product was dried at $20^{\circ}/0.2$ mm for 6 hours. A grey-coloured product was obtained which turned white on exposure. [Found: Al, 6.44; Cl, 15.62. $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{43}\text{COO})$ requires Al, 6.42; Cl, 16.25%].

Aluminium Trilaurate.—Aluminium chloride (2.60 g., 1M) was refluxed with lauric acid (14.70 g., 4M) in benzene (60 ml) at the bath temperature $115^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$ for nearly 21 hours. A white product separated from the solvent, which was dried under reduced pressure (0.2 mm) at 60° .

The product was refluxed with dioxan (75 ml) for 5 minutes. A white product separating on cooling was washed repeatedly with dioxan and dried at $55^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}/0.5$ mm. [Found: Al, 4.36. Calc. for $\text{Al}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}\text{COO})_3$: Al, 4.33%].

Aluminium Tripalmitate.—Benzene (60 ml) was distilled in the mixture of aluminium chloride (1.60 g., 1M) and palmitic acid (9.45 g., 3M). The mixture was refluxed for 40 hours in a bath at $105^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$. The white product separating was washed and dried under reduced pressure (0.2 mm) at 60° . [Found: Al, 3.35. Calc. for $\text{Al}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}\text{COO})_3$: Al, 3.41%].

The above product (2g.) was refluxed with dioxan (25 ml). A white product separated on cooling. (Found: Al, 3.39%).

Similarly, a mixture of aluminium chloride (1.83 g., 1*M*) and palmitic acid (12.70g., 4*M*) was refluxed in benzene (100 ml) in a bath at $110^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$ for 19 hours. The product was crystallised from benzene and dioxan. [Found: Al, 3.43. Calc. for $\text{Al}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}\text{COO})_3$: Al, 3.41%].

Aluminium Tribehenate.—Benzene (60 ml) was distilled in the mixture of aluminium chloride (1.33 g., 1*M*) and behenic acid (13.82 g., 4*M*). The mixture was refluxed in a bath at $105^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$ for 20 hours. A white product separating on cooling was washed and dried under reduced pressure (0.2 mm) at 45° for 3 hours. [Found: Al, 2.57. $\text{Al}(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{43}\text{COO})_3$ requires Al, 2.59%].

Aluminium Monolaurate Dipalmitate.—Benzene (50 ml) was added to a mixture of aluminium dichloride monolaurate (6.7g., 1*M*) and palmitic acid (11.55g., 2*M*). The mixture was refluxed for 36 hours in a bath at $120^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$. The volatile fraction was distilled and the product was dried at $25^{\circ}/0.5$ mm. The product was refluxed with dioxan. A white product separating on cooling was washed and dried. [Found: Al, 3.76. $\text{Al}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}\text{COO})(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{31}\text{COO})_2$ requires Al, 3.68%].

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